

A Method for Evaluating Future Plans and Aiding Decision-Making

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Abstract

This paper designs a method based on probability theory for evaluating future plans and aiding decision-making, and conducts application experiments. Questionnaires are used to ask two respondents, Jack and Eve, questions on the topics of postgraduate entrance exams and travel. The method is then applied to provide recommendations for their future plans. Both respondents express agreement with the recommended future plans.

Keywords: Future plans; Probability theory; Decision-making

1. Introduction

I found that in my previous paper "A Mathematical Model of Emotion and Future Planning" [1], the description of the future planning part lacked mathematical rigor and did not conform to the probability theory system. Therefore, this paper re-describes it using the language of probability theory. Additionally, "A Mathematical Model of Emotion and Future Planning" only gave one example, which did not fully demonstrate the function of the method, and it lacked experiments. Therefore, I used a questionnaire method to conduct experiments: for two topics, I asked two respondents, Jack and Eve, some questions, obtained tabular data, then used the method in this paper to analyze future plans, help them choose future plans, and finally obtained experimental results. In this paper, $(, \dots)$ represents an ordered pair, and $\{ , \dots\}$ represents a set.

2. Basic Concepts of Probability Theory Needed

The concepts in Chapter 2 are all taken from "Probability Theory and Mathematical Statistics Study Guide and Exercises" edited by Yang Zhoumu [2].

- (1) Random experiment: An experiment or observation of a characteristic of a random phenomenon is called a random experiment.
- (2) Sample point e : Each possible outcome of a random experiment is called a sample point.
- (3) Sample space S : The set composed of all sample points is called the sample space.

(4) Random event: A set composed of several sample points, or a subset of the sample space, is called a random event.

(5) Random event field \mathcal{F} : A set of certain random events we care about must be a σ -algebra to ensure closure under operations on events. For cases where the sample space is a finite set, the random event field generally takes the power set of the sample space (the set of all subsets), denoted as 2^S , where S is the sample space.

(6) Probability function P: The probability function P is a function from the random event field \mathcal{F} to $[0,1]$, satisfying the following three conditions:

1. Non-negativity: For any event $A \in \mathcal{F}$, $P(A) \geq 0$.
2. Normativity: The probability of the sure event is 1, i.e., $P(S) = 1$, where S represents the sample space.
3. Countable additivity: For any sequence of pairwise mutually exclusive events (A_1, A_2, \dots) , we have

$$P\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i\right) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} P(A_i)$$

(7) Probability space: A probability space is defined as a triple (S, \mathcal{F}, P) , where S is the sample space, \mathcal{F} is the random event field, and P is the probability function. For a random experiment, defining S, \mathcal{F}, P constitutes a complete probability space.

(8) Random variable: A random variable is a function from the sample space to R. Suppose the sample space of a random experiment is S. If for every sample point e in S, there is a unique real number corresponding to it, then this mapping is called a random variable.

3. A Method for Evaluating Future Plans Described Using Probability

Theory Language

Definition 1: Time node: Time is represented using the notation from physics, meaning a specific moment is represented by a single number. A time node is a specific moment in the future, a number.

Definition 2: Time set T: Select a finite number of time nodes to form the time set T.

This paper uses a finite number of discrete time nodes to approximately represent future time. When enough time nodes are taken densely enough, future time can be represented relatively accurately. Suppose T has m elements in total, then the time nodes can be represented as t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m , and T can be represented as $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$, with the rule $t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_m$

Definition 3: Matter: A set of the form $\{\emptyset_1\}, \{\emptyset_2\}$, or {a specific concrete matter}.

$\{\emptyset_1\}$ represents the research subject (the person executing the future plan) not doing anything. $\{\emptyset_2\}$ represents nothing happening around the research subject. The description of a matter should conform to mathematical norms, be rigorous, unambiguous, and free of paradoxes. Matters are considered non-continuous, considered to occur at an instantaneous moment. Even for continuous matters, such as studying for a period of time, this paper treats them as instantaneous; this has no impact on the results.

Definition 4: Matter set ET: Select a finite number of matters sufficient to cover the discussion topic to form the matter set ET.

Suppose ET has n elements, then matters can be represented as M_1, M_2, \dots, M_n , and ET can be represented as $ET = \{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_n\}$. Here, M is a constant. ET must include $\{\emptyset_1\}$ and $\{\emptyset_2\}$.

Future matters cannot be determined, but one can try to describe them using probability. This paper treats future matters as performing m random experiments (usually m non-independent random experiments, in special cases m independent random experiments). For the random experiment at each time node t_i , there is a sample space Ω_i , representing the set of all possible outcomes of the random experiment with non-zero probability. Extend each sample space Ω_i to ET, so that the sample space for each random experiment becomes exactly the same. Regarding the extension, it can be understood as follows: Ω_i is the set of all possible outcomes of the i-th random experiment. Include the impossible outcomes as well, but define the probability function so that the probability of these outcomes is 0. That is, we do not consider these outcomes as non-existent, but rather consider them as outcomes with probability 0.

To describe m random experiments, because of their general non-independence, they cannot be described separately but should be viewed as a single overall random experiment. The sample space of this overall random experiment is $ET^{(m)} = ET \times ET \times \dots \times ET$, the m-fold Cartesian product of ET, denoted as S, i.e., $S = ET^{(m)}$. The elements of S are sample points, denoted as ω , $\omega = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m)$, where $w_i \in ET$. Here, w is a variable. In contrast, the earlier M is a constant. Generally, w is used to denote a variable in ET, and M denotes a constant in ET. The random event field $\mathcal{F} = 2^S$ is the power set of S. Define a probability function P on the random event field \mathcal{F} , $P: \mathcal{F} \rightarrow [0,1]$. This constitutes a probability space (S, \mathcal{F}, P) .

Definition 5: Marginal probability function P_k : Define m functions $P_k: ET \rightarrow [0,1]$, k takes values 1,2,...,m, defined as follows:

$$\forall w \in ET, P_k(w) = P(ET \times \dots \times ET \times \{w\} \times ET \times \dots \times ET)$$

where w is in the k-th position, the multiplication sign represents the Cartesian product, and there are m-1 ET in total.

The meaning of the marginal probability P_k is the probability that the outcome takes the

value w in the k -th random experiment. From the definition and the countable additivity of P , we get $P_k(w) = \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} P(\{\omega\})$, where Ω is the set of all ordered pairs in $ET^{(m)}$ whose k -th position is w .

Definition 6: Conditional probability function P_k^* : Define m functions $P_k^*: ET^{(k)} \rightarrow [0,1]$, k takes values $1,2,\dots,m$, defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k) \in ET^{(k)}, P_k^*(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k) \\ = \frac{P(\{w_1\} \times \{w_2\} \times \dots \times \{w_{k-1}\} \times \{w_k\} \times ET \times \dots \times ET)}{P(\{w_1\} \times \{w_2\} \times \dots \times \{w_{k-1}\} \times ET \times ET \times \dots \times ET)} \end{aligned}$$

where the multiplication sign represents the Cartesian product. There are $m-k$ ET in the numerator and $m-k+1$ ET's in the denominator. $w_i \in ET$.

The meaning of $P_k^*(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k)$ is the conditional probability of w_k occurring under the condition that w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{k-1} have occurred. Therefore, it is also denoted as $P_k^*(w_k | w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{k-1})$. From Definitions 5 and 6, we get:

$$\forall \omega = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m) \in ET^{(m)}, P(\{(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m)\}) = P_1(w_1) \prod_{k=2}^m P_k^*(w_k | w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{k-1})$$

This is obtained by directly calculating the expression on the right-hand side from Definitions 5 and 6.

From normativity and countable additivity, we get $\sum_{\omega \in S} P(\{\omega\}) = 1$ and $\sum_{w \in ET} P_k(w) = 1$, where k takes values $1,2,\dots,m$.

Definition 7: Independence: If the probability function P satisfies

$$\forall \omega = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m) \in ET^{(m)}, P(\{(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m)\}) = \prod_{k=1}^m P_k(w_k)$$

then the probability function P is said to have independence.

Comparing Definition 7 with the previous equation, it is easy to see: if P has independence, then $\forall (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{k-1}), P_k^*(w_k | w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{k-1}) = P_k(w_k)$, where k takes values $1,2,\dots,m$. It is worth mentioning that according to the definition of independence in probability theory, events with probability 1 and events with probability 0 are independent of any event.

Definition 8: Non-repetitiveness: If the m marginal probability functions P_k derived from the probability function P satisfy:

- (1) $\forall w \in ET, \exists \text{unique } k_0, P_{k_0}(w) \neq 0$
- (2) $\forall w \in ET, \forall k \neq k_0, P_k(w) = 0$

Then the probability function P is said to have non-repetitiveness.

If P has non-repetitiveness, we get: (1) $P(\dots, a, \dots, a, \dots) = 0$. (2) If $P(\dots, a, \dots) \neq 0$, then $P(\dots, a, \dots) = 0$, where the second formula has a in a different position than the first formula. Proof of (1) uses proof by contradiction. Suppose $P(\dots, a, \dots, a, \dots) \neq 0$. Suppose the first a is

at the i -th position and the second a at the j -th position. Then $P_i(a) = \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} P(\{\omega\}) \geq P(\dots, a, \dots, a, \dots) > 0$. Similarly $P_j(a) > 0$, contradicting the uniqueness of k_0 . (2) is directly obtained from the definition.

From equations (1) and (2) in the previous paragraph, it can be seen that the meaning of P having non-repetitiveness is that matters in ET only have a non-zero probability of occurring at a single time node, and cannot have a non-zero probability of occurring at two time nodes.

Definition 9: Value of a matter E : E is a numerical value measuring the value of a matter. The value is positive if the matter is positive for the research subject, and negative if the matter is negative for the research subject. The meaning of E can take many forms. When only considering the economic value of a matter, the meaning of E can be taken as money. When needing to consider human emotions, the meaning of E can be taken as emotional value [1].

$\{\emptyset_1\}$ and $\{\emptyset_2\}$ are listed separately because their E is 0. It can be understood as follows: When the meaning of value is emotional value, $\{\emptyset_1\}$ means the research subject (let it be Jack) does not do anything. Here, "anything" refers to matters that cause Jack's emotions. Jack is sleeping or accustomed to what they are doing; these matters do not cause Jack's emotions. As for matters that can cause Jack's emotions, Jack does not do them. $\{\emptyset_2\}$ means nothing happens around the research subject. Here, "things" also refer to matters that cause Jack's emotions. The things happening around Jack are irrelevant to Jack (according to Lazarus's theory of emotion appraisal [3], Jack's primary appraisal of the things results in the things being irrelevant to Jack, thus the emotional value is 0), or Jack is accustomed to them, and they do not cause Jack's emotions. As for the things around Jack that cause Jack's emotions, they do not happen. When the meaning of value is money, the meaning of $\{\emptyset_1\}$ is that Jack does not do anything that would lead to monetary gain or loss. The meaning of $\{\emptyset_2\}$ is that nothing happens around Jack that would lead to monetary gain or loss. "Not doing anything" and "nothing happening" in $\{\emptyset_1\}$ and $\{\emptyset_2\}$ do not mean absolutely nothing, but rather that there are no matters with non-zero E .

E is related to the research subject (person), time, and the matter itself. Different people have different value judgments about the same matter. The same person at different times may also have different value judgments about the same matter. Suppose the research subject is Jack. For Jack, the value of matter w occurring at time t can be denoted as $E(\text{Jack}, t, w)$, where $t \in T, w \in ET$.

Definition 10: Intrinsic value of a matter V : Define a numerical value $V(w)$ that is only related to the matter itself, representing the intrinsic value of the matter, which depends on the essence of the matter.

Definition 11: Characteristic value m : Suppose the research subject is Jack. m is a state quantity describing Jack's attitude (or appraisal) towards matter w at time t . Defined $asm(\text{Jack}, t, w) = \frac{E(\text{Jack}, t, w)}{v(w)}$, where $t \in T, w \in ET$. $m(\text{Jack}, t, w)$ is also denoted as $m_w(\text{Jack}, t)$.

When the meaning of value is emotional value, $E(Jack, t, w) = m_w(Jack, t)V(w)$ can be used to explain the phenomenon of the influence of past matters on the emotional value (or called the interaction of emotions) caused by the present matter. Two matters do not influence each other across time; rather, past matters affect Jack's current state through Jack's memory, i.e., $m_w(Jack, t)$, which in turn affects the emotional value caused by w , i.e., E . For example, if Jack is bitten by a snake and encounters a snake again later, due to past memory, the absolute value of $m_M(Jack, t)$ is generally larger than for a person encountering a snake for the first time, Jack's absolute value of E is also larger, and the reaction is stronger.

In some special cases, V is independent of w , then $E(Jack, t, w) = m(Jack, t)V(w)$. In this case, $m(Jack, t)$ can be seen as a quantity describing Jack's state at time t (such as mood, long-term joy or sadness).

The form of the above equation is very similar to a method commonly used in differential equations called separation of variables. This inspires us to further classify variables under more special circumstances: $E(Jack, t, w) = m_1(Jack)m_2(t)V(w)$

When the research subject Jack is given, E is a mapping from $T \times ET$ to R . Once this mapping is determined, a numerical value can be defined for each sample point $\omega = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m)$ of the sample space S . This defines a function, defined specifically as follows.

Definition 12: Total value function $E_{total}: E_{total}: S \rightarrow R$, $E_{total}(\omega) = \sum_{i=1}^m E(Jack, t_i, w_i)$, where $\omega = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m) \in S, w_i \in ET, t_i \in T, T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$.

According to the definition of a random variable, E_{total} is a random variable.

This paper selects the average value of E_{total} as the numerical value for evaluating future plans, choosing the future plan with the largest value. The average value of E_{total} is defined as follows.

Definition 13: Average total value $\overline{E_{total}}: \overline{E_{total}} = \sum_{\omega \in S} E_{total}(\omega)P(\{\omega\})$.

Definition 14: Types of matters: Matters can be divided into Type I and Type II according to different properties. Type I matters are things that people actively do. Type II matters are things that happen passively around people.

Type I matters are subjectively decided by people, such as studying hard, eating, swimming, etc. Type II matters are not subjectively decided by people, but their conditional probability of occurrence is generally influenced by people's active behaviors, such as exam results, natural disasters, etc. The marginal probability and conditional probability of Type I matters can only take values 0 or 1. Type I matters are independent of any matter. The marginal probability and conditional probability of Type II matters can take values in the range $[0,1]$. Matters in ET can be divided without overlap into a set of Type I matters and a set

of Type II matters. The former is denoted as ET_1 , the latter as ET_2 . $\{\emptyset_1\} \in ET_1, \{\emptyset_2\} \in ET_2$.

Time nodes are also divided into Type I and Type II. The types of time nodes are selected in advance, and their properties are reflected by the following rule. All probability functions are stipulated to satisfy that at Type I time nodes, only the marginal probabilities of Type I matters are non-zero, and the marginal probabilities of Type II matters are all zero. At Type II time nodes, only the marginal probabilities of Type II matters are non-zero, and the marginal probabilities of Type I matters are all zero.

Next is the definition of a future plan. Before this, select some time nodes from the time set T and designate their type as Type I. The remaining time nodes are designated as Type II. Suppose a total of k Type I time nodes are selected, arranged in increasing order as $t_{i_1}, t_{i_2}, \dots, t_{i_k}$.

Definition 15: Future plan: Choosing one element from ET_1 for all Type I time nodes constitutes a future plan. Different choices are different future plans. The Type I time nodes are the same for different future plans. A future plan is defined as an ordered pair $((t_{i_1}, w_1), (t_{i_2}, w_2), \dots, (t_{i_k}, w_k))$, where $t_{i_1}, t_{i_2}, \dots, t_{i_k}$ are the pre-selected Type I time nodes, arranged in increasing order, and $w_i \in ET_1$.

The three elements of the probability space plus E_{total} constitute the four elements of the probability space (S, F, P, E_{total}) . For different future plans, S, F, E_{total} are the same, but P is different. If the future plan is $((t_{i_1}, w_1), (t_{i_2}, w_2), \dots, (t_{i_k}, w_k))$, the marginal probabilities derived from the probability function satisfy $P_{i_\mu}(w_\mu) = 1, P_{i_\mu}(w) = 0 (w \in ET \text{ and } w \neq w_\mu)$, where μ takes values $1, 2, \dots, k$. That is to say, for each future plan, at each Type I time node, the matter in the future plan corresponding to that time node must occur, and all other matters must not occur. It can be seen that different future plans have different probability functions. After defining the matter set ET and the function E_{total} on $ET^{(m)}$, but before the future plan is determined, the probability function P cannot yet be defined. After the future plan is determined, the probability function P can be defined, and the four elements are completely defined. Each future plan corresponds to one four-element set. The four-element sets corresponding to different future plans differ only in P; the others are the same. That is, the main framework is the same, only the function defined on the framework is different. After the four-element set is determined, the expected value of E can be calculated.

The following describes the steps of the method for evaluating future plans:

1. Select a finite number of time nodes to define T. Select a finite number of matters to define ET.
2. From ET, obtain $S = ET^{(m)}, \mathcal{F} = 2^S$.
3. Define a function $E_{total}: S \rightarrow R$.
4. Select some time nodes. Suppose k are selected. Designate their type as Type I. The remaining time nodes are designated as Type II.

5. For the k Type I time nodes, sequentially select k elements from ET_1 to form a future plan. Different selections are different future plans.

Note: Denote the future plans as FP. Suppose there are u future plans in total, denoted as FP_1, FP_2, \dots, FP_u .

6. For each future plan FP_i , define a probability function $P_i: \mathcal{F} \rightarrow R$. A total of u functions.

Note: In fact, P_i only needs to be defined on S (actually on the set of singleton subsets of S).

7. For a future plan FP_i , a four-tuple $(S, \mathcal{F}, P_i, E_{total})$ is defined. After the four-tuple is defined, the $(\overline{E_{total}})_i = \sum_{\omega \in S} E_{total}(\omega) P_i(\{\omega\})$ corresponding to FP_i can be calculated. $\overline{E_{total}}$ serves as the numerical value for evaluating the future plan. Compare the $\overline{E_{total}}$ of the u future plans. The FP_i with the largest $\overline{E_{total}}$ is the recommended future plan.

Note: The u future plans correspond to u four-tuples. Among these four-tuples, only P is different. The other elements $S, \mathcal{F}, E_{total}$ are all the same.

Figure 1 Future matters path diagram. Simplified

Simplified, let $ET = \{a, b, c, d\}$. Each path corresponds to a probability P and a total value E_{total} . Combine all paths to calculate the expected value of E_{total} .

Suppose $ET = \{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_n\}$, $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$, then the future matters path diagram

can be represented by an $n \times m$ matrix, namely $\begin{pmatrix} M_1 & \dots & M_1 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ M_n & \dots & M_n \end{pmatrix}$. This matrix is a

non-numerical matrix; each element is a set rather than a number, and the m elements in each row are the same. This non-numerical matrix is called the framework of the topic under discussion.

When the research subject Jack is given, the value function E is a mapping from $T \times ET \rightarrow R$. From the function E we can obtain an $n \times m$ matrix whose matrix elements are $E_{ij} = E(t_j, M_i)$. This matrix is also denoted as E, i.e., $E = (E_{ij})$.

From the probability function $P: \mathcal{F} \rightarrow R$ we can obtain m marginal functions $P_k(w) = P(ET \times \dots \times ET \times \{w\} \times ET \times \dots \times ET)$. From this we can obtain an $n \times m$ matrix whose matrix elements are $P_{ij} = P_j(M_i)$. This matrix is also denoted as P, i.e., $P = (P_{ij})$.

That is to say, for each cell of the future matters path diagram (i.e., each element of the so-called framework, a non-numerical matrix) there corresponds a value and a probability, thus forming two $n \times m$ numerical matrices E and P.

Suppose the probability function P satisfies independence, then $P(\{(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m)\}) = \prod_{k=1}^m P_k(w_k)$, where $(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m) \in ET^{(m)}$. In the formula $\overline{E_{total}} = \sum_{\omega \in S} E_{total}(\omega)P(\{\omega\})$, ω is an element of $ET^{(m)}$, can be expressed as $\omega = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m)$, where $w_i \in ET$, w is a variable. Suppose $(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m) = (M_{i_1}, M_{i_2}, \dots, M_{i_m})$, where w is a variable, M is a constant. Here the arbitrariness of w is represented by the arbitrariness of the subscript i , because each element in ET corresponds one-to-one with a subscript, and each element can be represented by a subscript.

$$\text{Then } P(\{(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m)\}) = \prod_{k=1}^m P_k(w_k) = \prod_{j=1}^m P_j(M_{i_j}) = \prod_{j=1}^m P_{i_j j}$$

$$\text{Furthermore, } E_{total}(\omega) = E_{total}(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m) = \sum_{k=1}^m E(t_k, w_k) = \sum_{j=1}^m E_{i_j j}.$$

Substitute the two expressions above into the expression for V, summing over all paths, we obtain:

$$\overline{E_{total}} = \sum_{i_m=1}^n \sum_{i_{m-1}=1}^n \dots \sum_{i_1=1}^n \left(\left(\prod_{j=1}^m P_{i_j j} \right) \left(\sum_{j=1}^m E_{i_j j} \right) \right)$$

$\overline{E_{total}}$ is uniquely determined by the future plan, can be called the value of the future plan, represented by the letter V.

Next, simplify the formula.

Since the latter summation term $\left(\sum_{j=1}^m E_{i_j j} \right)$ contains m terms, we can split this overall multiple summation into m mutually independent parts, obtaining:

$$V = \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i_m=1}^n \sum_{i_{m-1}=1}^n \dots \sum_{i_1=1}^n \left(\left(\prod_{j=1}^m P_{i_j j} \right) (E_{i_j j}) \right)$$

Here we use the commutativity of independent summation Σ .

For the j-th term split out, we extract the variable $E_{i_j j}$ related only to i_j , obtaining:

$$V = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\sum_{i_j=1}^n (P_{i_j j} E_{i_j j}) \times \left(\sum_{\substack{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m \\ \text{except } i_j}} \prod_{k=1}^m (P_{i_k k}) \right) \right)$$

Here we use the formula for multiplication of sums $\left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i\right)\left(\sum_{j=1}^m b_j\right) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m a_i b_j$.

Note that the part inside the parentheses contains $m-1$ -fold summation, and these product terms are respectively related only to different columns of P , therefore can be written as a product of individual summations, obtaining:

$$V = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\sum_{i_j=1}^n (P_{i_j j} E_{i_j j}) \times \left(\prod_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq j}}^m \left(\sum_{i_k=1}^n P_{i_k k} \right) \right) \right)$$

Here we use the formula for multiplication of sums $\left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i\right)\left(\sum_{j=1}^m b_j\right) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m a_i b_j$.

From the normalization of marginal functions $\sum_{w \in ET} P_k(w) = \sum_{i=1}^n P_k(M_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n P_{ik} = 1$, holds for any k . That is, for any k , $\sum_{i_k=1}^n P_{i_k k} = 1$. From this we obtain:

$$V = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\sum_{i_j=1}^n (P_{i_j j} E_{i_j j}) \right) = \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n P_{ij} E_{ij}$$

In the last step, i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m are all summed from 1 to n , therefore we can use a single letter i to represent them.

Writing V in matrix form gives:

$$V = \text{tr}(P^T E) = \text{tr}(E^T P) = 1_n^T (P \odot E) 1_m$$

Where tr denotes the trace of the matrix, $P^T E$ is matrix multiplication, \odot is the Hadamard product (element-wise multiplication of matrices), which is commutative, 1_n denotes an n -dimensional column vector of all ones. The first equality can be obtained by directly writing out $\text{tr}(P^T E)$, the latter two equalities are conclusions in linear algebra, also obtained by direct calculation.

The originally so complicated formula for V can actually be simplified to such a concise form as $V = \text{tr}(P^T E)$. The deeper meaning here will be explored. The part $\prod_{j=1}^m P_{i_j j}$ can be viewed as the product of multi-dimensional independent discrete probabilities. The $\sum_{j=1}^m E_{i_j j}$ in the original formula is the summation of the E values corresponding to this set of random trials. The meaning of V is the expected value of the sum of the E values corresponding to m independent random variables. Since the expectation can be written in summation form: $V = E\left(\sum_{j=1}^m E_{i_j j}\right)$, where \mathbb{E} denotes expectation. According to the linearity of expectation, we can directly move the summation sign outside: $V = \sum_{j=1}^m \mathbb{E}\left(E_{i_j j}\right)$. In a single column, the expectation $\mathbb{E}\left(E_{i_j j}\right)$ equals $P_{ij} E_{ij}$, substituting gives: $V = \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n P_{ij} E_{ij}$. This double

summation is precisely the sum of all elements of the element-wise product (Hadamard product) of matrices E and P, which in linear algebra is equivalent to $tr(P^T E)$.

Here we discuss the meaning of the formula $V = tr(E^T P)$. Its meaning is that the value of the future plan equals value multiplied by probability, which in probability theory is the meaning of expected value, embodying the core idea of this method: "calculate the expected value of value over all possible paths". But in the formula $V = tr(E^T P)$, both E and P are matrices, which is similar to the representation of mechanical quantities by matrices in quantum mechanics.

Suppose the function E is independent of time, i.e., for any $w \in ET, E(t_1, w) = E(t_2, w) = \dots = E(t_m, w) = E(W)$. This condition, when expressed on the matrix E, means that each column of matrix E is equal, therefore E can be represented by a column matrix composed of

a certain column of elements $e = \begin{pmatrix} E(M_1) \\ \vdots \\ E(M_n) \end{pmatrix}$. Then V is expressed as:

$$V = e^T \cdot P \cdot 1_m$$

Where " \cdot " denotes matrix multiplication. This is obtained from $V = 1_n^T (P \odot E) 1_m$, and $1_n^T (P \odot E) = 1_n^T (E \odot P) = e^T \cdot P$ (obtained by direct calculation).

If the probability function P has non-repetitiveness, by definition the matrix P has only one non-zero element per row.

Definition 16: if a matrix P has only one non-zero element per row, call this matrix non-repetitive.

Place $\{\emptyset_1\}, \{\emptyset_2\}$ at the very front of ET, i.e., $M_1 = \{\emptyset_1\}, M_2 = \{\emptyset_2\}$. Partition the matrix P as $P = \begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \end{pmatrix}$, where P_1 has only 2 rows. In a relatively common case, matters in ET other than $\{\emptyset_1\}, \{\emptyset_2\}$ can only possibly occur at a single time node, with marginal probabilities zero at other time nodes. This means that the matrix P_2 has non-repetitiveness. Restricting the domain of the probability function P to $2^{(ET - \{\emptyset_1\}, \{\emptyset_2\})^m}$ (which is a subset of the original domain $\mathcal{F} = 2^{(ET)^m}$) yields a new probability function P_2 (alternatively, from the matrix P_2 and independence conditions we can construct a new probability P_2). This new probability function P_2 has non-repetitiveness in the functional sense. Suppose the n-2 non-zero elements of matrix P_2 form an (n-2)-dimensional column vector p . Suppose the first two rows of e form a new 2-dimensional column vector e_1 , and the remaining n-2 rows form a new (n-2)-dimensional column vector e_2 . Then V can be expressed as

$$V = e^T \cdot P \cdot 1_m = (e_1^T \ e_2^T) \begin{pmatrix} P_1 \\ P_2 \end{pmatrix} \cdot 1_m = e_1^T \cdot P_1 \cdot 1_m + e_2^T \cdot p$$

Where we used block matrix multiplication and for a matrix P_2 in which each row has only one non-zero element, we have $P_2 \cdot 1_m = p$ (obtained by direct calculation).

In summary, we obtain expressions for V under various conditions, listed as follows:

1. Probability function P has independence: $V = tr(E^T P)$.

2. Probability function P has independence and E is independent of time: $V = e^T \cdot P \cdot 1_m$.

3. Probability function P has independence and E is independent of time, and matters in ET other than $\{\emptyset_1\}, \{\emptyset_2\}$ can only possibly occur at a single time node, with marginal probabilities zero at other time nodes (i.e., restricting the domain of the probability function P to $2^{(ET - \{\{\emptyset_1\}, \{\emptyset_2\}\})^m}$ yields a new probability function P_2 that has non-repetitiveness): $V = e_1^T \cdot P_1 \cdot 1_m + e_2^T \cdot p$.

To summarize, the most important things in this method are two $n \times m$ matrices: the value matrix E and the probability matrix P . Different future plans have different matrices P , but the same matrix E , and the same non-numerical matrix called the framework. Different matrices P give different future plans different V values (future plan value).

Under the condition that the probability function P has independence. The logic of the method is as follows. First, define the matter set ET from the topic under discussion, and from ET define the non-numerical matrix called the framework. Second, the research subject gives the value matrix E . Then, for each future plan, give the probability matrix P . The system, for each future plan, uses the formula $V = tr(E^T P)$ to calculate the V value (the value of the future plan, also the value for evaluating the future plan), and selects the future plan with the largest future plan value as the recommendation.

4 Application Experiment of the Method for Evaluating Future Plans

I used questionnaires to ask two respondents, Jack and Eve, on the topics of postgraduate entrance exams and travel respectively. For each person and each topic, one value table and three probability tables were obtained. Only Jack's postgraduate exam case is described in detail. For the others, only the data and results are given. For ease of calculation, it is stipulated that the probability function P_i for each future plan satisfies independence and non-repetitiveness. This requires a good selection of ET so that matters under each future plan are mutually independent and non-repetitive.

Define $T = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4\}$, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4 are in increasing order. The specific time numbers are actually not important; what matters is the number and order. These time nodes serve as the carrier or scaffold for matters.

Define $ET_1 = \{\{\emptyset_1\}, \{\text{study hard for 3 months}\}, \{\text{spend 20,000 yuan to enroll in a class}\}, \{\text{relax and entertain for 3 months}\}\}$. For short, denote them in order as $ET_1 = \{\emptyset_1, a, b, c\}$.

Define $ET_2 = \{\{\emptyset_2\}, \{\text{be broken up with}\}, \{\text{successfully pass the postgraduate exam}\},$

$\{\text{fail the postgraduate exam}\}\}$. For short, denote them in order as $ET_2 = \{\emptyset_2, d, e, f\}$. $ET =$

$ET_1 \cup ET_2 = \{\emptyset_1, a, b, c, \emptyset_2, d, e, f\}$.

The value table obtained from Jack's questionnaire is as follows (the meaning of value here is emotional value, obtained by comparing matters with losing/gaining 10,000 yuan to get the emotional value. The definition of the unit: positive unit one is the emotional value of gaining 10,000 yuan, negative unit one is the emotional value of losing 10,000 yuan):

\emptyset_1	study hard for 3 months	spend 20,000 yuan to enroll in a class	relax and entertain for 3 months	\emptyset_2	be broken up with	successfully pass the postgraduate exam	fail the postgraduate exam
0	-2	-2	1	0	-2	10	-1

Table 1 Jack postgraduate exam value table

Select t_1, t_2 as Type I time nodes, and t_3, t_4 as Type II time nodes. Sequentially select 2 elements from ET_1 for the 2 Type I time nodes to form a future plan. Different selections are different future plans. Excluding unreasonable ones and those that do not satisfy non-repetitiveness, three future plans remain: Future Plan 1 (FP_1): (a, b) ; Future Plan 2 (FP_2): (a, \emptyset_1) ; Future Plan 3 (FP_3): (c, \emptyset_1) (the time nodes are omitted here because they are the same for all Type I time nodes).

Use a table to represent the sample space. Each column represents a time node. Each broken line from left to right corresponds to an ordered pair (each position in the ordered pair has 8 choices), which is an element of the sample space. There are a total of 8^4 elements.

\emptyset_1	\emptyset_1	\emptyset_1	\emptyset_1
a	a	a	a
b	b	b	b
c	c	c	c
\emptyset_2	\emptyset_2	\emptyset_2	\emptyset_2
d	d	d	d
e	e	e	e
f	f	f	f

Table 2 Sample space table: Rows show matters

Below, the probability function for Future Plan 1 (FP_1): (a, b) is discussed. In this example, P satisfies independence and non-repetitiveness. According to the definition of independence, P can be obtained from the marginal probabilities. Defining the marginal probability function defines P. According to the definition of non-repetitiveness, the marginal probability function for each matter is non-zero at only one time node. Additionally, because the sample space for each random experiment has been extended to include matters with zero marginal probability, the matters with non-zero marginal probability at the same time node should be the possible outcomes of a certain random experiment and should have correlation.

Through the above considerations, define P such that $P_1(a), P_2(b), P_3(d), P_3(\emptyset_2), P_4(e), P_4(f)$ are non-zero, and all other marginal probabilities are zero. (One could also define P such that $P_1(a), P_2(b), P_3(e), P_3(f), P_4(d), P_4(\emptyset_2)$ are non-zero, and all other marginal probabilities are zero. This only changes the order compared to the

original definition, with no essential difference.)

Next, let Jack fill out a questionnaire (Jack estimates probabilities based on his own experience and inquiries with AI) to obtain the probability table (the probabilities here refer to the unique non-zero marginal probabilities of matters; if there is no non-zero one, fill in 0).

probability table for Future Plan 1(FP_1): {{study hard for 3 months}, {spend 20,000 yuan to enroll in a class}}		
be broken up with	successfully pass the postgraduate exam	fail the postgraduate exam
0.7	0.6	0.4

Table 3 Probability questionnaire for Future Plan 1

\emptyset_1	a	b	c	\emptyset_2	d	e	f
0	1	1	0	0.3	0.7	0.6	0.4

Table 4 Complete probability table for Future Plan 1

From Future Plan 1, we get $P_1(a) = 1, P_2(b) = 1$. The marginal probabilities of other Type I matters are all 0. \emptyset_2 is special. Its marginal probability is not obtained from Jack's questionnaire but is calculated from $P_3(d)$ combined with the fact that the sum of marginal probabilities at each time node is 1. The same applies not only to this case but also to others. This is due to the special nature of \emptyset_2 itself; the probability of nothing happening cannot be estimated in advance.

From Table 4, we get $P_1(a) = 1, P_2(b) = 1, P_3(d) = 0.7, P_3(\emptyset_2) = 0.3, P_4(e) = 0.6, P_4(f) = 0.4$. All other marginal probabilities are 0. Then, using the independence of P, we obtain the probability function P:

$$P(a, b, \emptyset_2, e) = 1 \times 1 \times 0.3 \times 0.6 = 0.18$$

$$P(a, b, \emptyset_2, f) = 1 \times 1 \times 0.3 \times 0.4 = 0.12$$

$$P(a, b, d, e) = 1 \times 1 \times 0.7 \times 0.6 = 0.42$$

$$P(a, b, d, f) = 1 \times 1 \times 0.7 \times 0.4 = 0.28$$

All other 4092 elements of the sample space have probability 0. It can be seen that the probability function P is normalized. It can also be seen that the number of non-zero elements in the sample space equals the product of the number of outcomes with non-zero marginal probability for each of the m random experiments.

From the value table, obtain the E_{total} of these four elements of the sample space:

$$E_{total}(a, b, \emptyset_2, e) = -2 - 2 + 0 + 10 = 6$$

$$E_{total}(a, b, \emptyset_2, f) = -2 - 2 + 0 - 1 = -5$$

$$E_{total}(a, b, d, e) = -2 - 2 - 2 + 10 = 4$$

$$E_{total}(a, b, d, f) = -2 - 2 - 2 - 1 = -7$$

The other 4092 elements of the sample space have $P=0$ and thus do not contribute to the average value of E_{total} , so there is no need to calculate their E_{total} .

Calculate $\overline{E_{total}}$:

$$\overline{E_{total}} = \sum_{\omega \in S} E_{total}(\omega)P(\{\omega\}) = 0.18 \times 6 + 0.12 \times -5 + 0.42 \times 4 + 0.28 \times -7 = 0.2$$

Thus, $(\overline{E_{total}})_1 = 0.2$.

Using matrix calculation, here all are 8×4 matrices. The non-numerical matrix called the framework is

$$\begin{pmatrix} \emptyset_1 & \emptyset_1 & \emptyset_1 & \emptyset_1 \\ \emptyset_2 & \emptyset_2 & \emptyset_2 & \emptyset_2 \\ a & a & a & a \\ b & b & b & b \\ c & c & c & c \\ d & d & d & d \\ e & e & e & e \\ f & f & f & f \end{pmatrix}, E = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -2 & -2 & -2 & -2 \\ -2 & -2 & -2 & -2 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -2 & -2 & -2 & -2 \\ 10 & 10 & 10 & 10 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, P = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.3 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.7 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.4 \end{pmatrix}. \text{ For matrix P, its last}$$

n-2 rows need to be given, while its first two rows are obtained through the fact that the sum of all elements in each column is 1 (1 minus the sum of the values in the other rows). Whether this value goes into the first row or the second row depends on the type of this time node. This is a general conclusion regarding the probability matrix P. Using the formula $V = tr(E^T P)$ to calculate, we get $V = \overline{E_{total}} = 0.2$, which is consistent with the $(\overline{E_{total}})_1$ calculated earlier using each path. This further verifies the correctness of $V = tr(E^T P)$.

For Future Plans 2 and 3, only the probability tables need to be changed; the rest is similar to Future Plan 1.

probability table for Future Plan 2 (FP_2): $\{\{\text{study hard for 3 months}\}, \{\emptyset_1\}\}$		
be broken up with	successfully pass the postgraduate exam	fail the postgraduate exam
0.7	0.5	0.5

Table 5 Probability questionnaire for Future Plan 2

	P	E_{total}
$(a, \emptyset_1, \emptyset_2, e)$	0.15	8
$(a, \emptyset_1, \emptyset_2, f)$	0.15	-3
(a, \emptyset_1, d, e)	0.35	6
(a, \emptyset_1, d, f)	0.35	-5

Table 6 P and E_{total} for Future Plan 2

Thus, $(\overline{E_{total}})_2 = 1.1$.

probability table for Future Plan 3 (FP_3): $\{\{\text{relax and entertain for 3 months}\}, \{\emptyset_1\}\}$		
be broken up with	successfully pass the postgraduate exam	fail the postgraduate exam
0.3	0.01	0.99

Table 7 Probability questionnaire for Future Plan 3

	P	E_{total}
$(c, \emptyset_1, \emptyset_2, e)$	0.007	11
$(c, \emptyset_1, \emptyset_2, f)$	0.693	0
(c, \emptyset_1, d, e)	0.003	9
(c, \emptyset_1, d, f)	0.297	-2

Table 8 P and E_{total} for Future Plan 3

Thus, $(\overline{E_{total}})_3 = -0.49$

$(\overline{E_{total}})_2 > (\overline{E_{total}})_1 > (\overline{E_{total}})_3$, Recommend that Jack choose Future Plan 2: $\{\{\text{study hard for 3 months}\}, \{\emptyset_1\}\}$.

For the other respondent, Eve, only the three probability tables and one value table need to have their numerical values modified. The other steps are exactly the same as before. The data and results are as follows.

\emptyset_1	study hard for 3 months	spend 20,000 yuan to enroll in a class	relax and entertain for 3 months	\emptyset_2	be broken up with	successfully pass the postgraduate exam	fail the postgraduate exam
0	-10	-2	2	0	-10	5	-1

Table 9 Eve postgraduate exam value table

probability table for Future Plan 1(FP_1): $\{\{\text{study hard for 3 months}\}, \{\text{spend 20,000 yuan to enroll in a class}\}\}$		
be broken up with	successfully pass the postgraduate exam	fail the postgraduate exam
0.5	0.7	0.3

Table 10 Eve Future Plan 1 probability table

probability table for Future Plan 2 (FP_2): $\{\{\text{study hard for 3 months}\}, \{\emptyset_1\}\}$		
be broken up with	successfully pass the postgraduate exam	fail the postgraduate exam
0.5	0.6	0.4

Table 11 Eve Future Plan 2 probability table

probability table for Future Plan 3 (FP_3): $\{\{\text{relax and entertain for 3 months}\}, \{\emptyset_1\}\}$		
be broken up with	successfully pass the postgraduate exam	fail the postgraduate exam

0.1	0.1	0.9
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Table 12 Eve Future Plan 3 probability table

$(\overline{E}_{total})_1 = -13.8$, $(\overline{E}_{total})_2 = -12.4$, $(\overline{E}_{total})_3 = 0.6$, Recommend that Eve choose Future Plan 3: $\{\{\text{relax and entertain for 3 months}\}, \{\emptyset_1\}\}$.

For the topic "travel", suppose Jack and Eve need to choose a travel destination. Define $T = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4\}$. t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4 are in increasing order. The specific time numbers are actually not important; what matters is the number and order. These time nodes serve as the carrier or scaffold for matters.

Define $ET_1 = \{\{\emptyset_1\}, \{\text{go to Thailand}\}, \{\text{go to Japan}\}, \{\text{go to the USA}\}\}$. For short, denote them in order as $ET_1 = \{\emptyset_1, a, b, c\}$. Define $ET_2 = \{\{\emptyset_2\}, \{\text{encounter robbery}\}, \{\text{encounter natural disaster}\}, \}$. For short, denote them in order as $ET_2 = \{\emptyset_2, d, e\}$. $ET = ET_1 \cup ET_2 = \{\emptyset_1, a, b, c, \emptyset_2, d, e\}$.

Select t_1 as a Type I time node, and t_2, t_3 as Type II time nodes. Sequentially select 1 element from ET_1 for the 1 Type I time node to form a future plan. Different selections are different future plans. Since they already plan to travel, exclude $\{\emptyset_1\}$. Finally, three future plans remain: Future Plan 1 (FP_1): (a); Future Plan 2 (FP_2): (b); Future Plan 3 (FP_3): (c) (the time nodes are omitted here because they are the same for all Type I time nodes).

Jack's one value table and three probability tables are as follows:

\emptyset_1	go to Thailand	go to Japan	go to the USA	\emptyset_2	encounter robbery	encounter natural disaster
0	12	10	8	0	-1	-100

Table 13 Jack travel value table

probability table for Future Plan 1 (FP_1): $\{\{\text{go to Thailand}\}\}$	
encounter robbery	encounter natural disaster
0.002	0.001

Table 14 Jack Future Plan 1 probability table

probability table for Future Plan 2 (FP_2): $\{\{\text{go to Japan}\}\}$	
encounter robbery	encounter natural disaster
0.0003	0.02

Table 15 Jack Future Plan 2 probability table

probability table for Future Plan 3 (FP_3): $\{\{\text{go to the USA}\}\}$	
encounter robbery	encounter natural disaster
0.005	0.04

Table 16 Jack Future Plan 3 probability table

	P	E_{total}
(a, d, e)	0.000002	-89
(a, d, \emptyset_2)	0.002	11
(a, \emptyset_2, e)	0.001	-88
$(a, \emptyset_2, \emptyset_2)$	0.997	12

Table 17 Jack Future Plan 1 P and E_{total}

$(\overline{E}_{total})_1 \approx 11.898$, $(\overline{E}_{total})_2 \approx 7.996$, $(\overline{E}_{total})_3 \approx 3.976$, recommend that Jack choose Future Plan 1: $\{\{\text{go to Thailand}\}\}$.

Eve's one value table and three probability tables are as follows:

\emptyset_1	go to Thailand	go to Japan	go to the USA	\emptyset_2	encounter robbery	encounter natural disaster
0	6	8	9	0	-1	-50

Table 18 Eve travel value table

probability table for Future Plan 1 (FP_1): $\{\{\text{go to Thailand}\}\}$	
encounter robbery	encounter natural disaster
0.002	0.001

Table 19 Eve Future Plan 1 probability table

probability table for Future Plan 2 (FP_2): $\{\{\text{go to Japan}\}\}$	
encounter robbery	encounter natural disaster
0.0003	0.02

Table 20 Eve Future Plan 2 probability table

probability table for Future Plan 3 (FP_3): $\{\{\text{go to the USA}\}\}$	
encounter robbery	encounter natural disaster

0.005	0.04
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Table 21 Eve Future Plan 3 probability table

$(\overline{E}_{total})_1 \approx 5.948$, $(\overline{E}_{total})_2 \approx 6.997$, $(\overline{E}_{total})_3 \approx 6.987$, recommend that Eve choose Future Plan 2: $\{\{\text{go to Japan}\}\}$.

5. Conclusion

This paper, based on probability theory, designs a method for evaluating future plans and aiding decision-making, and conducts application experiments. Two respondents, Jack and Eve, are asked questions on two topics, postgraduate entrance exams and travel, using questionnaires. This method is then used to provide recommendations for their future plans. Both respondents Jack and Eve expressed agreement with the recommended future plans.

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